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OPTIMIZATION AND SIGNIFICANCE OF ULTRASOUND SOUND DIAGNOSTICS IN SELECTION OF TACTICS IN TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH NECK OSTEOCHONDROSIS (literature review)

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ANNOTATION

Cervical osteochondrosis is a degenerative disease of articular cartilages, which is one of the key causes of pain in the neck region with characteristic irradiation to the arms. In this disease there is a change in the structure of cartilage and musculo-ligamentous structures located nearby.

Keywords: ultrasound examination, cervical osteochondrosis, neurological examination

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ОПТИМИЗАЦИЯ И ЗНАЧЕНИЕ УЛЬТРАЗВУКОВЫХ МЕТОДОВ ДИАГНОСТИКИ В ВЫБОРЕ ТАКТИКИ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ БОЛЬНЫХ С ШЕЙНЫМ ОСТЕОХОНДРОЗОМ (литературный обзор)

АННОТАЦИЯ

Шейный остеохондроз — дегенеративное заболевание суставных хрящей, выступающее одной из ключевых причин возникновения болезненности в области шеи с характерной иррадиацией в руки. При этом заболевании отмечается изменение структуры хрящей и мышечно-связочных структур, расположенных поблизости.

Ключевые слова: УЗИ исследование, шейный остеохондроз, неврологические исследования

Усаров Мухриддин Шухратович
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БЎЙИН ОСТЕОХОНДРОЗИ БЎЛГАН БЕМОРЛАРНИ ДАВОЛАШ ТАКТИКАСИНИ ТАНЛАШДА УЛЬТРАТОВУШ ДИАГНОСТИКАСИ УСЎЛЛАРИНИН ОПТИМИЗАЦИЯСИ ВА АҲАМИЯТИ (АДАБИЁТЛАР ШАРҲИ)

АННОТАЦИЯ

Бўйин остеохондрози — бўғим кемикларининг дегератив касаллиги бўлиб, бўйин соҳасида оғрик пайдо бўлишига сабаб бўлувчи асосий омиллардан биридир ҳамда қолларга тарқалиши билан белгиланади. Бу касалликда хрящлар ва яқин атрофдаги мушак-сегман таркиби ўзгаришлари кузатилади.

Калит сўзлар: ультратовуш текшируви, бўйин остеохондрози, неврологик текширув

Introduction. Diagnostic examination makes it possible to identify atherosclerotic plaques, narrowing and widening of the lumen, inflammatory processes and congenital anomalies. The diagnostic procedure is not accompanied by radiation exposure to the body.

Since, as cervical osteochondrosis progresses, it can lead to a number of severe complications up to the disability of the patient, his timely diagnosis and treatment are among the urgent tasks of modern medicine. Our clinic is equipped with modern equipment, and the staff is represented by experienced specialists with extensive knowledge about this disease, which allows them to provide assistance to all patients.

Often the cause of headaches are diseases of the blood vessels. In most cases, they develop in middle and older age. Due to insufficient blood supply to the brain, there are signs of ischemia. These include: memory impairment, decreased performance, sleep disorders. To diagnose ischemia, Doppler sonography of the vessels of the brain and neck is performed. Among them are large arteries and veins originating from the aortic arch.

Brachiocephalic vessels (BCS) are the carotid, subclavian and vertebral arteries, as well as the brachiocephalic trunk. They form a Willis circle, which evenly distributes blood to various parts of the

brain. When pathological disorders occur in one of these vessels, there is a violation of blood circulation in the brain area.

Most often, deviations are observed from the vertebral arteries running along the lateral surface of the cervical vertebrae. Mechanical compression leads to difficulty in getting blood into the Willis circle and the brain, respectively. Pathologies of the cervical spine can lead to irritation of the cervical nerve plexus. This leads to a spasm of the vascular walls and a decrease in their lumen. In the complex, this condition is called vertebral artery syndrome.

Atherosclerosis is also the cause of impaired circulatory processes in the BCG – plaques of various sizes formed in the walls of blood vessels. They lead to a decrease in the lumen and are accompanied by an increase in cholesterol levels in the blood.

Ultrasound determines the pathology of the vessels of the head and neck. The study can be conducted in patients of all ages. Vascular dopplerography is an instrumental research method based on determining the speed of blood flow. Thanks to these diagnostic procedures, it is possible to show how affected the arteries and veins are, as well as the degree of narrowing of the lumen.

Methods of ultrasound diagnostics:

- Traditional. It is aimed at determining the geometry of vessels, their patency and the diameter of the lumen.

- Dopplerography (UZDG). It shows a real-time picture of blood flow. A color picture is created on the screen, from which the doctor starts to determine the speed of blood flow and identify narrowing, atherosclerotic plaques and blood clots.

Ultrasound diagnostics allows you to determine the degree of vascular patency. Also, based on the results obtained, it is possible to assess the correspondence of the position of the structures to the desired trajectory. Ultrasound reveals neoplasms (cholesterol plaques) that interfere with the movement of blood. The procedure determines the condition of the soft tissues located next to the veins and arteries.

The essence of the study is to scan the arterial or venous system. The image will appear on the monitor. Traditional ultrasound allows you to assess the condition of the endothelium and the lumen of the arteries of the head and neck. Duplex scanning is more complicated. It improves visualization.

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Instrumental diagnostics of the vessels of the neck is carried out using a complex of triplex and duplex scanning. The methods are aimed at determining the characteristics of the blood flow of the vessels of the head and neck, including intracranial ones. The monitor displays a complete picture of soft tissues with an image of arteries and veins.

The choice of scanning method depends on which area of the vascular bed needs to be examined. Each of them is effective in diagnosing certain diseases.

Methods of ultrasound examination of blood vessels:

- Carotid ultrasonography. Vessels in the neck are examined with the help of a special device. This type of visualization is the most common. It is prescribed if a neurological disease associated with insufficient nutrition of the brain is suspected. The vessels of the neck are superficial, the largest of them are the carotid arteries. Ultrasound of the carotid artery reveals the cause of dizziness, fainting, sleep and memory disorders, and neurological symptoms.

- Transcranial ultrasound Dopplerography. When scanning, the sensor is located in the occipital and temporal regions. Using this method, the anterior, posterior, middle and vertebral arteries are examined. Allows you to assess the condition of the rectus sinus, the veins of Galen and Rosenthal.

- Transorbital ultrasound of the arteries. The sensor is located on the upper eyelid. With this access, blood flow in the circulatory and orbital arteries is assessed.

The examination lasts 20-40 minutes. There is no discomfort during the diagnosis process. Only a minimal feeling of pressure in the head and neck area is possible.

The procedure of ultrasound examination of the head and neck consists of several stages:

1. The patient lies on his back on the medical couch.
2. A special gel is applied to the skin of the examined area, designed to better conduct ultrasound waves.
3. If necessary, the specialist asks the patient to hold his breath, breathe frequently or turn his head in the right direction.

When examining the carotid artery, it is necessary to turn the head to the right or left and tilt it back slightly. The sensor is located in the area of large and medium-sized vessels. At full duplex, the vessels penetrating into the cranial cavity are examined. To do this, the patient is asked to take a sitting position. To assess the condition of the cerebral arteries, the sensor is installed behind the auricle. The study of the rectus sinuses, Rosenthal and Galen veins, and cerebellar vessels is carried out in the occipital region.

There is no need for special training. It is enough to give up alcohol and smoking 1-2 days before the study. First, you need to consult with your doctor about taking vascular medications. Otherwise, the result may be distorted.

Decryption of the result

Ultrasound examination of the vessels of the head and neck visualizes the main arteries that provide nutrition to the brain. The ultrasound protocol includes a decoding of the anatomical features of vascular structures. It also includes information about the movement of blood flow, deformities or obstruction of arteries and veins.

Vascular ultrasound diagnoses the following pathologies and abnormalities:

- Impaired blood circulation of the brain. It occurs due to thrombosis, narrowing of veins and arteries, as well as due to changes in blood flow rate and with the development of osteochondrosis. The determination of hypoxia at the initial stage of development helps to prevent complications, such as stroke.

- Thrombosis. Fibrin protein and platelets accumulate in certain areas of the vessels. A blood clot completely or partially blocks the lumen of an artery or vein, which is fraught with circulatory disorders, the development of hypoxia and dangerous consequences.

- Atherosclerotic plaques. At the very beginning of the blockage formation, the vascular wall thickens to 1.5 mm. If the indicators increase, then we are talking about the presence of plaque.

The optimal indicator of intima media is 0.9. It is acceptable to increase it to 1.1 mm. If the value exceeds 1.3 mm, the doctor concludes that there is an atherosclerotic growth. In addition, normally the thickness of the arteries should be in the following ranges:

- Common carotid – 4.2-6.9 mm;
- External carotid – 3-6 mm;
- Internal carotid – 3-6.3 mm;
- Vertebrates – 3-4 mm.

Blood vessels should be smooth and have no thickening, deformations should be absent. The diagnosis takes into account the speed and nature of blood flow. During the period of tension in the common carotid artery, the indicator is 50-104 cm / sec., during relaxation – 9-36. The specialist evaluates the resistive and pulsation

index, systolic-diastolic ratio, and the degree of arterial stenosis. To diagnose the condition of veins, their diameter, lumen are taken into account, and phases of blood flow are detected depending on respiration and load.

Consultation. With the help of ultrasound examination of the brachiocephalic arteries, a specialist will be able to identify the existing

pathologies and organize the necessary treatment. If necessary, he will prescribe an additional examination for the patient. Among the advantages of ultrasound, it is possible to identify high information content and low cost.

List of literature

1. Akatov, O. V. Percutaneous radiofrequency destruction of articular nerves in the treatment of lower lumbar pain / O. V. Akatov, O. N. Dreval, Yu. N. Kononov // Questions of neurosurgery 2017-No. 2.-pp. 17-20.
2. Akimov, G.A. Compression-ischemic peroneal neuropathies (Guillain-De Seza-De syndrome Blondin-Walter)/ G.A. Akimov, A.A. Mikhashenko// Journal. Neuropathol. And psychiatrist. 2016 -No.6. - pp.96-102.
3. Baklanov, A.N. Diagnosis and treatment of the syndrome of the operated spine: abstract. diskand. med. sciences/AN. Cormorants. — Ufa, 2004. -20 p.
4. Belenky, A. G. Dorsalgia in degenerative diseases of the spine / A. G. Belenky//Russian Medical Journal.-2022 Vol. 10, No. 22 — pp. 63-69.
5. Dmitriev, E. A. Diagnosis of intervertebral hernias using computed tomography of epidurography / E. A. Dmitriev, B. S. Yatsishin, V. A. Kuzmenko // Questions of neurosurgery. -2017.- No.4.- pp. 58-60.
6. Dotsenko, V. V. Diseases of the spine and their diagnosis / V. V. Dotsenko // Medicine.- 2003.- No. 3,- pp. 14-20.
7. Dudarev, A. L. Magnetic resonance imaging with an ultra—low field in the diagnosis of diseases of the spine and spinal cord / A. L. Dudarev, A.V. Kholin // Bulletin of radiology and radiology.-1991. —No.4.- pp. 69-73.
8. Zharkov, P.L. Osteochondrosis and other dystrophic changes of the spine in adults and children./ P.L. Zharkov. M., Medicine, 1994. -191 p.
9. Jolondz, M.Ya. Osteochondrosis — delusion / M.Ya. Jolondz // St. Petersburg: Lan, 1996. 105 p.
10. Zavelya, M.I. Diagnostics of osteochondrosis of the lumbar spine.: abstract of the dissertation of the Candidate of medical sciences / M.I. Zavelya. Kharkov, 1982.-28 p.

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